

PREVISIÓN DE LA DEMANDA MULTI-PAÍS PARA UNA EMPRESA FABRICANTE DEL SECTOR DE LA CONSTRUCCIÓN, BASADA EN VARIABLES EXTERNAS MACROECONÓMICAS EXTRAÍDAS DE FUENTES OPEN-DATA

MULTI-COUNTRY DEMAND FORECASTING FOR A COMPANY IN THE CONSTRUCTION SECTOR, BASED ON EXTERNAL MACROECONOMIC VARIABLES EXTRACTED FROM OPEN DATA SOURCES

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ABSTRACT:

Demand forecasting is a very important feature in companies since it provides valuable information for taking decisions about planning, pricing and business growth strategies. In this paper, multi-country demand forecasting for a company of the construction industry is carried out. In the case study, we analyze different external variables from open data sources of each country in order to reduce uncertainty in demand forecasting. The analysis is carried out with different univariate and multivariate methods. The results show how the consideration of external variables improves the forecasts. Finally, forecasts of different kinds of demand are evaluated using Syntetos, Boylan and Croston classification methodology.

Key words: Demand forecasting, forecast models, multivariate methods, accuracy indicators

RESUMEN:

La previsión de la demanda es un aspecto muy importante en las empresas ya que proporciona información muy valiosa de cara a la toma de decisiones sobre planificación, precios y estrategias de crecimiento empresarial. En este artículo, se realiza la previsión de la demanda multi-país de una empresa del sector de la construcción. En el caso de estudio, se analizan diferentes variables externas de fuentes open data de cada país para añadirlas en los modelos de previsión y así poder reducir la incertidumbre en la previsión de la demanda. El análisis se lleva a cabo con métodos de previsión univariantes y multivariantes. Los resultados muestran cómo la consideración de variables externas mejora los resultados de previsión. Finalmente, se evalúa la mejora de la previsión para distintos tipos de demanda por medio de la metodología de clasificación de Syntetos, Boylan y Croston.

Palabras clave: Previsión de la demanda, modelos de previsión, métodos multivariantes, indicadores de precisión

1.- INTRODUCTION

The presence of uncertainty in demand is a critical point that causes the development of increasingly complex forecasting models [1]. The set of activities aimed at providing estimates of a company's future sales is called demand forecasting and are a necessary element in the company's planning decision making. Warehouse inventory planning, transportation fleet sizing, resource allocation or task planning are some of the processes to be planned according to the results provided by the demand forecasting process.

Demand forecasting is key to decision making that leads to efficient supply chain behavior. Forecasting as closely as possible helps to reduce costs and improve profit. Numerous papers have been published that confirm this fact and show the need for adequate demand forecasting capabilities to improve supply chain performance and reduce the whiplash effect.

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The planning process is a critical factor in order to be able to offer a good and differentiating service to end customers. In construction machinery manufacturing companies, procurement lead times are much longer than the delivery times requested by customers. The company must have the foresight to anticipate needs and thus be able to better manage the supply chain, in order to finally be able to deliver the products demanded within the deadlines required by the increasingly competitive market.

In a supply chain there are a multitude of factors external to historical demand data that can cause uncertain changes in the patterns of the series and thus influence its behavior. The company in the construction industry under study serves globally, supplying construction machinery to countries all over the world. The demand for the products can be influenced by macroeconomic variables that are different in each country (gross domestic product, price index, etc.). Incorporating these factors into forecasting models could lead to more effective results.

Two categories of methods can be distinguished according to the number of variables used:

- Univariate methods: They require a single data series, so they require the estimation of a smaller number of parameters in the models and the fit is simpler.
- Multivariate methods: Less frequent, they allow to include in the models, not only the historical of the variable to be predicted, but also other time series that may affect the future, allowing to improve forecasts.

In principle, the incorporation of a larger number of explanatory variables in a forecasting model and the use of a multivariate method will make it possible to obtain more accurate demand forecasts. Multivariate methods also allow the analysis of the dynamic relationship between the response variable and the explanatory variables involved in the same supply chain process. According to Lutkepohl [2], the objectives of the application of multivariate methods are twofold:

- Improve forecasting accuracy through new functions that incorporate exogenous variables into the historical series.
- Learn about the dynamic interrelationships between the variable to be predicted and other variables involved in the supply chain processes.

Multivariate forecasting methods are still little used because they have more parameters to be estimated and, therefore, model selection is more complex. However, authors agree that multivariate methods are convenient to adequately model interdependencies and thus reach a better fit [3]. Fildes [4], in a review of leading forecasting journals, also recognizes the research possibilities that exist in multivariate forecasting.

The general objective of this work is to apply multivariate forecasting methods using real-time information from different variables to estimate future demand and to see if these variables help to improve the accuracy of classical univariate methods. It is proposed to design advanced regression methods, capable of modeling complex interrelationships between variables, as well as artificial intelligence or machine learning methods that capture patterns of interrelationships between variables in the past, in order to project them into the future. The use of information obtained from external data sources in real time will make it possible to incorporate into the forecasting models different types of information published in national and international sources capable of providing great value in the estimation models. This information, which will be specific to the sector (construction GDP, cement prices...) will be automatically extracted from online databases made available to the public by different official bodies (National Institute of Statistics, Bank of Spain, etc.).

Forecasting is performed with different time series models and artificial intelligence (deep learning). Forecasting results are evaluated with different accuracy indicators. In addition, the effectiveness of external variables is evaluated through the Syntetos, Boylan and Croston [5] methodology, which aims to analyze the methods evaluated according to the type of demand, for which they propose a demand classification based on the variability and intermittency of the series.

The article is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature on multivariate forecasting applied to logistics management. Section 3 describes the forecasting methodology. Section 4 includes the obtained forecasting results and the methodology is applied [5].

2.- LITERATURE REVIEW

In the demand forecasting process, models with high accuracy are sought since this has a great impact on the performance of the organization because it improves many processes along the supply chain [6]. One of the techniques that have good results when performing demand forecasting are multivariate methods since they include multiple time series that can contribute favorably to demand forecasting in the future. Some authors such as Fildes & Stephan Kolassa [6] state that, in general, multivariate studies show substantially better accuracy in forecasting at SKU level with respect to univariate methods. In Trapero et al [7] it was shown

that in the context of demand forecasts with promotional activity it is desirable to include additional information in the statistical models.

The influence of external variables in improving demand forecasting in different sectors can be observed in different studies. Table 1. shows different examples of the application of multivariate forecasting.

Authors	Scope of application	External variables	Multivariate model	Target
Nguyen-Le, Kim, Shin, Little 2021 [8]	Chemistry	1.Pressure 2.Porosity and permeability 3.Gas saturation 4.Adsorbed gas content 5.Mid-length fracture 6.Fracture spacing 7.Fracture conductivity	RSM Multivariate polynomial approach	Understanding the relationship between early production and long-term gas production
Maruyama, Yamamoto 2021 [9]	Hydrology	1.Maximum daily temperature 2.Maximum daily temperature squared 3.Temperature difference between today and yesterday. 4.Rain in the morning/5.Rain in the afternoon. 6.Cloudy in the morning/7.Cloudy in the afternoon. 8.Cloudy after the sun in the morning 9.Cloudy after sunshine in the afternoon 10.Sunshine after cloudy in the morning 11.The sun after the cloud in the afternoon	Multiple regression	Water demand forecasting
Jimenez, Palma, Sanchez, Marin, Palacios, Lopez, Jimenez, Palma, Sanchez, Marin, Palacios, Lopez 2020 [10]	Medicine	1.MRSA (methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus) 2.SA (Methicillin-sensitive Staphylococcus aureus) 3.Influence of having a second infection. 4.Oseltamivir 5.Levofloxacin	Multi objective Evolutionary Search	Understanding antimicrobial resistance
Casella 2019 [11]	Aerodynamics	1.Wind speed 2.Wind direction	Linear regression MMS	Wind forecast
Aboagye-Sarfo, Mai, Sanfilippo, Preen, Stewart, Fatovich 2015 [12]	Sanitary	1.Age groups 2.Triage category 3.Disposition (admitted/transferred/not admitted)	VARMA Winters	Sizing the emergency department

Table 1. Examples of multivariate forecasting applications in different sectors

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In the logistics area, more and more articles consider multivariate methods. Fantazzini & Toktamysova [13] relate the sales forecast of German cars to aspects such as consumer price index or oil price. Other authors, such as Abolghasemi et al. [14] or Kourentzes & Petropoulos [15] collect events such as sales promotions or days between promotions to carry out demand forecasting with multivariate methods such as ARIMA in the first case and multivariate MAP in the second. In the transportation sector, Plakandaras et al. [16] forecast the demand for air, road and rail transportation in the US domestic market by taking into account external variables such as total domestic shipments of US airlines on scheduled passenger flights, vehicle miles traveled or fuel cost with multivariate methodologies based on artificial intelligence.

In the case study of this article, different external variables that may be related to the construction sector are analyzed, something novel since no publications with multivariate demand forecasts applied to this sector have been found in the literature review. The variables under study are the gross domestic product (GDP) of the real estate sector, cement manufacturing and construction GDP. These data are specific to each country and will therefore take different values.

3.- FORECASTING METHODOLOGY

Forecasting models are appropriate for the generation of scenarios that correspond to plausible future developments. Demand forecasting can be defined as the construction of models that make it possible to estimate as accurately as possible the sales volume of a product, sector, or field within a given future period of time.

There are different forecasting methods, but in this case multivariate methods will be used. With these techniques, the different variables under study are modeled by representing the state of the system at different points in time. Thus, the forecasting models are adapted to the behavior of the demand considering the evolution of these variables.

For forecasting future demand, we used the methodology defined in Figure 1, based on the methodology used in [17].

First, the scope of the case under analysis is defined in order to determine the number of data series to be processed. Next, the objectives are defined, specifying the steps to be followed and the tools to be used. After data capture, the analysis of variables is carried out in order to identify whether there is a certain correlation between the variables under study. The test design specifies the methods and procedures used in the evaluation, as well as the temporal scope of the tests. The last step of the methodology corresponds to obtaining forecasts and analyzing the results obtained.

The following sections describe the different stages of the analysis in the case study.

Figure 1. Forecasting methodology

3.1.- SCOPE OF THE PROBLEM

The case study is based on a real distribution network of machinery products for the construction sector. This network is composed of a manufacturing company located in the north of Spain that supplies products from its facilities to all countries in the world. The company supplies some 500 types of machines to its customers on a daily basis to cover the orders of its globally distributed customers.

Given the competition in the sector, the company seeks to anticipate future demand in the different countries in order to plan its operations and be able to deliver products as soon as possible after they are ordered.

The case study focuses on the monthly supply of 36 products in the following set of 15 countries: France, Poland, Spain, Germany, Belgium, United Kingdom, Russia, Romania, Portugal, Netherlands, Bulgaria, Chile, Kenya, Hungary and the Philippines. In total there are series 213 corresponding to the different product-country combinations. The missing combinations are due to the fact that not all selected products are sold in all defined countries.

Figure 2. Demand of the company's countries analyzed in the case study (Tableau - or country flows)

3.2.- DEFINITION OF OBJECTIVES

The objective of the analysis is to evaluate the impact obtained with the introduction of variables external to the company in the demand forecasting process. In particular, it aims to verify whether the incorporation of macroeconomic information in the forecasting models improves the accuracy of the estimates. To this end, different measures of accuracy will be used to test whether the forecast obtained using external data sources improves the accuracy of other methods. The forecast tests will be performed with Forecast PRO XE and Python libraries.

3.3.- DATA CAPTURE

In the case study, three external data sources related to the construction sector were selected. Table 2 is shown with the variables identified, the location of these sources, the temporal aggregation of the information, the length of the historical and the availability or not of forecast data. Finally, GDP-Construction was selected as the external variable since it was the only one among those selected with monthly temporal aggregation, a history with an adequate length and availability of forecast data.

External variable	Source	Aggregation	Historical	Forecasts
GDP - Real Estate	[18]	Quarterly	1995-2021	Not available
Cement manufacturing	[19]	Monthly	2016-2017	Not available
GDP-Construction	[20]	Monthly	2018-2021	Available

Table 2. Characteristics of selected external variables available

To capture the GDP-Construction data series from the Trading Economics website, the *Trading Economics Application Programming Interface API (TE API)* was used, which provides direct access and downloadability of updated historical and forecast data. The download was done via the *Trading Economics Excel Add-In (TE Excel Add-In)* which connects Excel to the *TE API* providing direct access to the indicators.

The input parameters for the extraction of historical information and forecasts are as follows:

- Country
- Indicator
- Time interval (only for historical values)

Figure 3. Data chart screen and search screen in the TE Excel Add-In

The system returns in Excel the value of the indicator corresponding to the defined country and time interval.

3.4.- ANALYSIS OF VARIABLES

The objective of the analysis of variables is to observe whether there is any relationship between the sales series and the Construction GDP data series for each country. To this end, the evolution of the aggregate sales variable of all products in each country is analyzed graphically with the GDP indicator. From the analysis, it is detected that there is a strong correlation between the sales trend and the Construction GDP series. The following graphs show the evolution of both variables for Spain, the United Kingdom, Romania and Russia.

Figure 4. Sales vs. GDP trend graphs for Construction in Spain, UK, Romania and Russia

In order to quantify the dependence between the two variables, the Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated. This index is used to measure the degree of relationship between two variables as long as both are quantitative. The value of the coefficient, which can vary between -1 and 1, will be close to 0 if there is no correlation between them. Table 3 shows the correlation coefficient between construction GDP and sales trend for the 15 countries evaluated. It can be seen that in 87% of the cases the value taken by this coefficient is greater than 0.5, 67% of the cases being above 0.8, which confirms the existence of correlation.

Country	Correlation coefficient
United Kingdom	0,9464
Kenya	0,9440
Spain	0,9389
Netherlands	0,9113
Philippines	0,9051
Philippines	0,8813
Romania	0,8719
Freance	0,8634
Belgium	0,8461
Russia	0,8203
Portugal	0,6907
Bulgaria	0,6515
Poland	0,5294
Chile	0,4679
Germany	0,3787

Table 3. Correlation coefficient between sales trend and construction GDP

3.5.- TEST DESIGN AND FORECASTING PROCESS

3.5.1.- Forecasting models

The analysis of the case study aims to analyze the impact of the incorporation of external variables on the forecast. The assessment of the impact of external variables on the accuracy obtained by the models will be carried out by comparing the results obtained by two multivariate models with respect to a reference univariate model.

(1) Univariate model

An ARIMA (AutoRegresive Integrated Moving Average) model has been selected because it is one of the most advanced univariate methods. Its name derives from its three components AR (Autoregressive), I (Integrated) and MA (Moving Averages). The ARIMA model is a statistical model that uses variations and regressions of statistical data in order to find patterns for a prediction into the future. Future estimates are explained by past data and not by independent variables.

(2) Multivariate time series based on forecasting model

As a time series method, a dynamic regression model has been selected, which is an advanced regression method that includes w autoregressive terms of the output variable, z lag terms of the independent variables and v autoregressive error terms.

$$Y_t = a + b_1 Y_{t-1} + \dots + b_w Y_{t-w} + c_1 X_{t-1} + \dots + c_z X_{t-z} + d_1 \epsilon_{t-1} + \dots + d_v \epsilon_{t-v}$$

Equation 1. Multivariate Forecasting Model

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Model fitting in a dynamic regression method is a complex task, since each variable must be analyzed for each type of term (autoregressive of the output, autoregressive of the dependent variable and lags of the independent variables). For this reason, the Forecast Pro XE tool [21] has been used for model fitting.

(3) Multivariate forecasting model based on artificial intelligence

Within artificial intelligence models, the great potential of Deep Learning stands out [22]. Deep Learning algorithms use so-called neural networks to find associations between a set of inputs and outputs, the main types of layers being the following:

- Dense layer: used to combine all available information.
- Convolutional layer: used to extract important features or patterns
- Long short-term memory (LSTM): Used to find long-term correlations.
- Dropout: used to prevent overtraining

Figure 5. Diagram of a neural network and parameters used

Mei-Li Shen et al.[23] demonstrated the superiority of LSTM-based Deep Learning models over ten other time series forecasting and machine learning methods in a 10-country export and import forecasting case.

In our case, the best result has been obtained with a first LSTM layer with 100 units followed by another LSTM layer with 50 units. A Dropout layer is applied with the rate of 0.2 and a dense layer is applied as output with one unit with the active linear function. Figure 5 shows the architecture of the created deep network. The network has been trained for 80 epochs. The dataset has been divided into 29 months of training and 3 months of testing, reserving 10% of the training data for validation of results.

3.5.2.- Accuracy measures

The evaluation of model accuracy can be performed by means of two types of accuracy measures:

- Absolute accuracy measures: They express an absolute percentage of accuracy between the actual value and the forecast value.
- Relative accuracy measures: They express a relative percentage of accuracy between the actual value and the forecast value.

The case study uses a measure of absolute precision (*Mean Absolute Deviation or MAD*) and a measure of relative accuracy (*Forecast Accuracy or FA*).

(1) MAD

It is the method of forecast evaluation that uses the sum of simple errors or, in other words, the mean absolute deviation. MAD measures forecast accuracy by averaging the absolute value of each error.

$$MAD = \text{abs}(\text{forecast} - \text{real})$$

Equation 2. MAD

(2) FA

The most common way to measure forecast accuracy is to compare the forecast results against actual values for the next period. The objective is to find values close to 1 in order to make favorable judgments about the selected forecast model.

$$FA = 1 - \left| \frac{\text{forecast} - \text{real}}{\text{real}} \right|$$

Equation 3.

3.5.3.- Syntetos, Boylan and Croston Methodology

In order to identify which are the series where the forecast is most improved thanks to external variables, a demand classification analysis will be carried out following the methodology proposed by Syntetos, Boylan and Croston [5]. These authors propose rules for categorizing demand series based on the calculation of two indicators:

- Coefficient of variation
- Intermittency

The coefficient of variation, also called Pearson's correlation coefficient, is a statistical measure that informs us about the relative dispersion of a set of data. It is an indicator of the variability of a series and its calculation is obtained by dividing the standard deviation by the absolute value of the mean of the set. Intermittency indicates the interruption of sales in certain time periods and is calculated as the average number of days without sales.

Syntetos, Boylan and Croston [5] categorize the references according to the quadrant in Figure 6, considering a threshold of 0.49 for the coefficient of variation and 1.32 for intermittency. Thus, the demand series are classified into the following typologies:

- Smooth: they have a coefficient of variation of less than 0.49 and an intermittency of less than 1.32.
- Erratic: have a coefficient of variation greater than 0.49 and an intermittency of less than 1.32.
- Lumpy: have a coefficient of variation greater than 0.49 and an intermittency greater than 1.32.
- Intermittent: have a coefficient of variation lower than 0.49 and an intermittency higher than 1.32.

Figure 6. Demand classification according to Syntetos&Boylan [5]

3.5.4.-Tests performed

The forecasting tests are based on the application of the forecasting models and the accuracy assessment measures on the 213 selected series. The comparison of the accuracy measures obtained for the univariate method and the multivariate methods will serve to indicate whether, in this case, the consideration of external variables is effective in the multi-country forecasting process. A history of 32 months was used to perform the tests. The forecast has been made for the last three months.

4.- ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

4.1.- FORECAST RESULTS BY COUNTRY

This section analyzes the impact of the external variables described in the previous section on the forecast accuracy. Accuracy is evaluated by means of the MAD and FA measures.

The table includes the forecast accuracy results for the demand for the products averaged across the different countries. From the data we conclude that the multivariate methods' forecasts have, on average, higher accuracy (62% accuracy) than the univariate methods (57%) in their country-level average. However, there are some cases where this is not the case, such as France, Germany, Hungary and the Philippines. In addition, the multivariate time series method provides better results on average (63%) than the artificial intelligence method (60%).

Country	Country	Series No.	MAD Univ	MAD Mul - ST	MAD Mul - IA	Accuracy Univ	Accuracy Mul - ST	Accuracy Mul- IA
1	France	36	128	236	272	76%	53%	47%
2	Poland	30	172	131	135	90%	93%	92%
3	Spain	36	1052	523	557	62%	85%	80%
4	Germany	28	56	80	85	79%	74%	73%
5	Belgium	34	141	86	98	57%	72%	69%
6	Netherlands	25	89	88	93	64%	74%	72%
7	United Kingdom	29	58	41	42	62%	68%	68%
8	Portugal	31	88	22	25	55%	88%	87%
9	Hungary	34	105	102	106	45%	41%	39%
10	Romania	23	137	179	185	56%	77%	76%
11	Bulgaria	32	25	35	31	72%	77%	73%
12	Russia	34	535	590	602	0%	0%	0%
13	Kenya	15	261	280	302	0%	11%	2%
14	Chile	14	286	276	299	62%	65%	59%
15	Philippines	12	127	126	136	68%	67%	64%
	AVERAGE		217	186	198	57%	63%	60%

Table 4. Results by country obtained from the forecast tests

The Figure 7 shows the improvement in the accuracy of multivariate forecasting with respect to univariate forecasting. In particular, the results obtained from the application of the dynamic regression method (time series) are included. The histogram shows the percentage of product-country combinations that have obtained each accuracy range. It can be seen that the red line (multivariate) is shifted to the right with respect to the black curve (univariate) since the number of skus with a high precision range is higher. In the box plot, it is observed that the median of the precision data is higher in the case of the multivariate forecast.

Figure 7. Demand-based classification for forecasting

4.2.- FORECAST RESULTS BY TYPE OF DEMAND

The Syntetos, Boylan and Croston analysis [5] provides the results shown in Table 4. It is observed that the demand 213 series at the product-country level can be divided into three types: smooth, erratic and lumpy. Of these, 206 references are of the intermittent and volatile type and only 7 are of the stable type.

This effect implies greater complexity in the forecasting process. Table 5 shows a higher accuracy in the product-country series categorized as stable (83%) than those series categorized as erratic or lumpy (with an accuracy of 72% and 57 % respectively). Likewise, it is observed that the improvement derived from the incorporation of external variables is higher in the erratic and lumpy series (15 and 19 points of improvement respectively) than in the stable series (9 points of improvement).

Type of demand	Number of items	For sale	Sales	MAD Univ	MAD Multiv Reg	Accuracy Univ [%].	Accuracy Mul - ST [%] [%] Accuracy Mul - ST [%] [%] Accuracy Mul - ST
Smooth	7	525	20%	187	94	74	83
Erratic	47	992	40%	579	341	57	72
Lumpy	159	935	40%	1206	675	38	57
Total	213	2595	100%	1972	1110	56	71

Table 5. Classification of demand series of the case study according to the Syntetos, Boylan and Croston categorization. [5]

5.-CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Demand forecasting models make it possible to anticipate future customer orders, facilitating the planning of operations. This collaborative and dynamic flow of information facilitates more effective decision making, resulting in greater efficiency.

In this paper, we analyze the impact of incorporating macroeconomic variables into forecasting models in the framework of a multi-country distribution network of construction machinery on the accuracy of forecasts. It is shown that, with this additional information, the forecasting models provide better results. It is also shown that multivariate time series models provide less error than those based

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on artificial intelligence techniques. By means of the Syntetos-Boylan-Croston methodology, it is shown that the improvement occurs in all types of demand, although the highest impact occurs in lumpy series. The implementation plan of the forecasting system in the company is planned in several phases, starting with the lumpy series, where it has proven to be most effective. The applicability of the system is ensured by updating the forecasts with a monthly review frequency.

In future work, new multivariate forecasting models that incorporate a larger number of external variables can be evaluated. The impact of a collaborative forecasting system that incorporates information from the supply chain customers themselves could also be analyzed.

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